

Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf pilots impact and evaluation framework

D4.2

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Acronyms

CREAM	Clear, Relevant, Economic, Adequate, Monitorable
CSISTA	Citizen Science Impact StoryTelling Approach
D#.#	Deliverable
DITOs	Doing It Together science (H2020 project)
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
F-2-F	Face-to-face
GAF	Governance Analytical Framework
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
ICTs	Information and Communication Technologies
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MICS	Measuring Impacts in Citizen Science (H2020 project)
ODI	Open Data Institute
PM_{2.5}	Particulate matter
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SD	Socio-demographic
SE	Socio-economic
SPICED	Subjective, Participatory, Interpreted, Cross-checked and compared, Empowering, Diverse
ToC	Theory of Change
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
UK	United Kingdom

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Executive Summary

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. This document describes the evaluation and impact assessment framework and related processes for Urban ReLeaf city pilots, which are the procedural and methodological basis for conducting and reporting on the outcomes of the ex-post-evaluation and assessment in the final year of the project. To build the framework, Urban ReLeaf follows the principles for consolidated impact assessment in citizen science, builds on the concept of a Theory of Change, and draws from rule-of-thumb criteria for impact assessment and indicator development.

The Urban ReLeaf pilots evaluation and impact framework is a multi-level and multi-purpose framework to address the intricacies of impact assessment as well as the diversity of aims and actors in the project, contextual variation of pilots unfolding in the different cities and the different audiences for the assessment results. It consists of four distinct building blocks:

1. Procedural monitoring of pilot implementation and respective outcomes towards anticipated project impacts with a focus on monitoring inclusive engagement targets.
2. Ex-post assessment of the joint impact of Urban ReLeaf city pilots on society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance, using the standardised MICS platform approach as well as dedicated and city-specific assessments of pilot impacts on governance and policy.
3. Exploratory cost-benefit analysis.
4. Communicating impact results to different audiences, using impact stories.

While such a multi-purpose and multi-level approach poses the risk of being too demanding, the framework tries to form effective synergies with related project activities (project reporting, communications, capitalising on prior activities for baselining etc.), make use of off-the-shelf methods and only tailors methodologies where relevant and necessary.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background – the Urban ReLeaf project and city pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process. Athens is undergoing a greening transformation with a new, citizen-powered tree registry providing critical data for better management of greenspaces. Cascais engages citizens in sharing perceptions and thermal comfort levels while using greenspaces to validate the effectiveness of its parks. Meanwhile in Dundee, a city facing increasing grey infrastructure in deprived areas, actions to enhance the accessibility of greenspaces are co-developed with citizens and stakeholders. Mannheim has a heat action plan to safeguard its most vulnerable residents but has identified critical data gaps. Citizen observations of trees and thermal comfort, when integrated with official data streams, will aid the delivery of climate adaptation measures. Riga engages diverse audiences to address concerns about air pollution and greenspace usage, to ensure better informed policies. Finally, in Utrecht, data on temperature, humidity and heat stress, collected by and for citizens, will help them shape effective mitigation strategies to reduce the urban heat island effect.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to outline and describe the evaluation and impact assessment framework and related processes for the Urban ReLeaf city pilots.

This framework provides the procedural and methodological basis for conducting and reporting on the outcomes of the ex-post-evaluation and assessment in the deliverable report *D4.10 Urban ReLeaf pilots evaluation report and impact briefs*. The evaluation framework includes, amongst others, the Urban ReLeaf's approach to capturing impacts to society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance using the MICS approach. More specific impacts of city pilots on urban governance and policy and the acceptance and uptake of citizen observations in public and authoritative processes are captured via a tailored approach. This report outlines the process for devising such a tailored approach. The final methodology and results will be published in D4.10. While this document briefly embeds the assessment framework and related processes in the wider context of impact assessment, it does not provide a generic introduction or overview of related terms¹.

1.3 Structure of the document

Chapter 2 of this document describes the underlying assumptions and guiding principles for building the Urban ReLeaf evaluation and impact framework as well as the framework itself. The chapters following present individual approaches and building blocks of the framework and how they are addressed in the project in more detail. Chapter 3 describes monitoring of project implementation and outcomes towards impacts with a focus on monitoring inclusive engagement targets. Chapter 4 describes the approach for measuring the wider joint impact of Urban ReLeaf city pilots on society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance, using the MICS platform approach as well as additional city-specific assessments of impacts on governance and policy. Chapter 5 outlines initial explorations towards a cost-benefit analysis and chapter 6 presents plans for communicating impact results to different audiences, using impact stories. Chapter 7 provides conclusions and next steps.

¹ For comprehensive introductory information, relevant glossaries and details, see e.g., Wehn et al., 2020, 2017.

2 Building the evaluation and impact assessment framework

2.1 Reasons for evaluating and measuring impact

There are many reasons for conducting evaluation and impact assessments of projects, research activities and other interventions. They can aid in the steering of the implementation process through recurring monitoring if the project is on track and to inform corrective project management decisions. They are used to present outcomes and impacts of actions, often beyond the immediate context. Amongst others, scientists, researchers and coordinators of research projects face increasing demands to ensure their projects are delivering impact beyond science itself, i.e., creating benefits and change in policy, society at large, the environment or business and technology. Within this “research ‘impact’ agenda” (Boswell and Smith, 2017) research funding organisations (such as the European Commission or UK Research Council) require demonstration of impacts to legitimising their investments in research and to direct future action and funds. Researchers increasingly depend on impact assessments to validate impact claims, demonstrate expertise as well as capabilities to valorise research for society, and to mobilise further funding. Implicit in these reasons are also assumptions about power and reputation as those who have the knowledge and (monetary) resources to create and demonstrate impact likely benefit from the reinforcing success cycle.

Urban ReLeaf deploys a multi-purpose evaluation and impact assessment, which includes project monitoring to ensure progress towards achieving set goals, as well as demonstrating the realised benefits. Ultimately, the project is interested in understanding, and at best showcasing the viability and transformative potential of its approach, linked with pragmatic prospects of continuous funding and more intrinsic rewards of contributing to a more democratic, inclusive and resilient world.

2.2 Challenges of evaluating and measuring impact

The different reasons and demands for impact evaluations and some of the common result-based methods assume that it is possible to measure impacts, e.g., the policy impacts at the end of a three-year transdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder research and innovation project. Some question this assumption at the core and suggest that largely, too simplistic models of the interdependence of e.g., research and policy are used as a basis for impact assessment (Boswell and Smith, 2017). Others identify the Theory of Change (ToC) approach as the most suitable way to account for inherent complexities and impact scenarios under uncertainty (Belcher and Halliwell, 2021; Belcher and Palenberg, 2018; Belcher et al., 2020; Wehn et al., 2020). In pragmatic terms, practitioners tasked with conducting an impact assessment are faced with related issues. They are, inevitably, faced with incomplete information about the complex cause-effect relationships within highly dynamical systems but required to identify causality and valid attribution of the project’s contributions to impact pathways via actions and outputs. At the same time, the interdependence and timing of impacts unfolding may reach well beyond a project’s lifetime, which makes it hard to assess. Furthermore, the grey and peer-reviewed literature is packed with different

classifications of impact and domain specific terminologies, such as first, second and third order impacts for assessing the effects of ICTs on environmental sustainability (Casal et al., 2004), micro, meso, macrolevel impacts to cluster impacts of citizen observatories (Hager et al., 2021) or permanent vs. non-permanent organisational change and impacts (Schäfer et al., 2021). While these classifications may be valid in context, considerable semantic and conceptual ambiguity remains in the use of terms such as impact, outcome and output and related notions of short-, medium- or long-term (Belcher and Halliwell, 2021). Lastly, preparing and conducting an evaluation and impact assessment can potentially disturb project implementation due to being too resource intensive and demanding and needs to be developed with efficiency in mind.

2.3 Guiding principles, criteria and underlying concepts

To address some of these challenges, Urban ReLeaf adopts the notion of a dynamic impact space and builds on the following supporting principles and models: the principles for consolidated impact assessment in citizen science (Wehn et al., 2021b), the concept of a ToC and related terminology as described by Belcher and Halliwell, 2021, and rule-of-thumb criteria for impact assessment and indicator development (Roche, 1999).

2.3.1 Six principles for consolidating impact assessment in citizen science

The topic of impact assessment in citizen science has received growing attention, especially in the last decade and efforts are underway to professionalise related theory and practice. Projects, researchers and citizen science practitioners have developed and implemented a range of impact assessment approaches to capture and communicate impacts of citizen science in different domains (Ceccaroni et al., 2022; Kieslinger et al., 2017; Passani et al., 2020; Somerwill and Wehn, 2022; Wehn et al., 2021a)². More recently, the topic of impact of citizen science has become a subject for meta-analyses, e.g., to identify common citizen science impact pathways and effects of participant diversity on impact potential (Pateman and West, 2023), to understand the influence of project design on citizen science impacts (Kirschke et al., 2023), or to analyse the state-of-the-art in citizen science impact assessment approaches and derive specific principles for consolidation (Wehn et al., 2021b). While these latter principles were primarily devised to inform the development of one common and consolidated approach for impact assessment in citizen science, Urban ReLeaf uses them as informative guidelines when devising a tailored framework. The principles are as follows:

Principle 1: Acknowledging a variety of purposes of citizen science impact assessment: Urban ReLeaf uses an evaluation and impact assessment framework which aims to reflect the complexity of the project by consisting of several building blocks, each serving a different purpose, context, and audience while at the same time, trying to implement it with reasonable effort.

Principle 2: Non-linear conceptualisation of impact journeys to overcome impact silos: Urban ReLeaf is a highly embedded project with ambitious goals and

² See Wehn et al., 2021b for a comprehensive overview of published impact assessment and evaluation approaches in citizen science.

collaborating well beyond academia not only with the public but also with public authorities. They are in themselves highly dynamic systems shaped by internal and political logic. This may affect all stages of the collaborative process and the potential of project interventions to trigger or accelerate change, also in unforeseen ways. Hence, Urban ReLeaf is exposed to in-situ processes and actors and expects impact journeys to be highly dynamic and have a degree of uncertainty. While the project needs to ensure that it understands the kind of change and impact it is looking for, the exact ways in which the change will become apparent may vary across cities and/or be unexpected. Hence, several aspects of the assessment framework will remain openly framed to avoid narrow vision caused by, e.g., too narrowly defined indicators.

Principle 3: Adopting comprehensive impact assessment data collection methods and information sources: Collecting data and information specifically for evaluation and impact assessment is an undertaking with the potential to move the focus of attention away from core activities and overwhelm projects with disproportional tasks and expectations. Urban ReLeaf will therefore, wherever possible, use existing material, data, and information sources within the project (deliverables, progress reporting, meeting minutes, communication and dissemination material, regular event logs etc.) to address evaluation of impacts and indicators as well as deploy additional data collection only where necessary³. Urban ReLeaf will also consider a range of human sources for its impact assessment and address relevant actors to engage in the assessments (e.g., citizens and public authorities). To reduce overall burden, the framework devised by Urban ReLeaf will consist of building blocks with variable demand and effort associated with their implementation, mixing readily available, off-the-shelf with more tailored approaches.

Principle 4: Moving beyond absolute impact: Urban ReLeaf will deploy a mixed-methods framework which can document impact relative to the project's context and case-specific objectives. Where more deterministic and fixed approaches are used (e.g., using a standardised quantification system, or quantitative indicators) complementary information will be provided to put these results in perspective.

Principle 5: Fostering comparison of impact assessment results across citizen science projects: To support comparability of impacts between citizen science projects, Urban ReLeaf will use existing standardised tools (e.g., MICS) as well as publish details about the tailored approaches to enable comparability, where of interest.

Principle 6: Cumulative enhancement of impact assessment theory and practice over time: Urban ReLeaf will contribute its experiences with developing and implementing the framework over time to the newly established ECSA working group on impact assessment and work together with other citizen science practitioners and researchers to collectively enhance and further consolidate underlying concepts and tools.

³ Additionally, Urban ReLeaf is rooted in Responsible Research and Innovation principles and – as a project funded by the European Commission – it is subject to GDPR compliance and ethical requirements such as the data minimisation principle. These requirements also fully apply to the evaluation and impact assessment activities.

2.3.2 Urban ReLeaf Theory of Change

The pilot evaluation and assessment framework is nested within a ToC conceptualisation of Urban ReLeaf which currently serves the project as a suitable approximation of the complexities of how non-linear change processes and subsequent impacts, triggered and/or affected by dedicated project activities, may unfold. While a ToC still emphasises unidirectional causal relationships towards realised benefits, it acknowledges contextual embedding, enabling as well as undermining factors outside the control of project actors, the decreasing influence of a project as interaction with other actors and processes increase, as well as the importance of people’s assumptions held about the change process and their ability to learn and adapt to changing circumstances (Belcher and Halliwell, 2021; van Es et al., 2015).

In its more simplistic form, the logic model or logic framework (also known as intervention logic, or results-chain approach) is used by the European Commission (EC), who has adopted the model to structure anticipatory impact conceptualisations in project proposals for the Horizon Europe funding programme as well as using the logic for EC-led procedural and summative evaluation of funded projects. According to this model, change and impacts unfold – briefly described – in the following sequence: Set Objectives trigger implementation of specific > Activities, which bring about tangible > Results/Outputs, which enable > Outcomes, which lead to > Impacts (LBG OIS Center, 2023; Wehn et al., 2020).

For the Urban ReLeaf pilot evaluation and impact assessment, as outlined in this report, a disaggregation of the ToC between overall project activities, performance and impacts and pilot specific outcomes and impacts is required. This also requires defining the scale and boundaries of the ToC for the city pilots jointly and individually and how “distant” and abstract the notion of impacts will be. Overall, the basic assumptions about unfolding of outcomes related to city pilots is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Generic activity stages and change process related to citizen science campaigns and city pilots

At the heart of the process are the design and implementation of citizen science and citizen observation campaigns in the six pilot cities with the aim to engage participants in an inclusive way to collect information and data that are taken up in urban planning and policy to ultimately improve urban planning for climate change adaptation to make

cities greener, more just and resilient for all. While the campaigns are one focal point of attention, all pilots include critical preparatory, accompanying, and follow-on activities to the observation campaigns themselves, such as stakeholder engagement, interviews and workshops, data ecosystem mapping and technology development, place-based pop-up community and culture labs and dedicated insights workshops. The assessment of impacts of the city pilots will have to be able to consider this multitude of activities and their effects.

2.3.3 CREAM and SPICED criteria

In addition to the six overarching principles, and the ToC conceptualisation, Urban ReLeaf also uses best-practice criteria for impact assessment development and exploration of indicators to check pragmatic suitability and operationalisability of approaches, such as CREAM and SPICED (Roche, 1999; World Bank, n.d). CREAM helps assess minimum viability of chosen approaches, while SPICED helps to consider other aspects which correspond to some of the core values of Urban ReLeaf, such as participation, empowerment and inclusion.

CREAM stands for:

- **Clear:** approach/indicators should be precise.
- **Relevant:** approach/indicators should be appropriate to the subject and evaluation.
- **Economic:** approach/indicators can be implemented at a reasonable cost.
- **Adequate:** approach/indicators can provide sufficient information on impacts.
- **Monitorable:** approach/indicators can be easily assessed, and amenable to independent validation.

SPICED stands for:

- **Subjective:** approach/indicators should allow to capture unique and critical insights from high-value sources (e.g., people with special roles or experience).
- **Participatory:** approach/indicators should be co-created with those who can best assess them, such as beneficiaries, local staff and other stakeholders.
- **Interpreted:** approach/indicators should be explainable to people foreign to the respective assessment context.
- **Cross-checked and compared:** approach/indicators should allow validation through cross-checking and comparison across indicators, and by using different sources, methods, and evaluators.
- **Empowering:** approach/indicators should be empowering and allow groups and individuals to reflect on a changing situation.
- **Diverse:** approach/indicators should be inclusive to allow points of view from different groups of people.

In Urban ReLeaf, the criteria are used in several ways. CREAM and SPICED are used to assess indicators for monitoring and evaluation of inclusive engagement in the city pilots (see chapter 3.3) and more prescriptively to help shape and determine the tailored approach for capturing city-specific impacts on policy and governance (see chapter 4.2). CREAM is used to evaluate the suitability of the MICS approach (see chapter 4.1) and prescriptively for the cost-benefit analysis (see chapter 5).

2.4 The framework in a nutshell

The Urban ReLeaf pilots evaluation and impact framework is a multi-level and multi-purpose framework to be able to address the intricacies of impact assessment as well as the diversity of aims and actors in the project, contextual variation of pilots unfolding in the different cities and the different audiences for the assessment results. Hence, the framework consists of four distinct building blocks (Figure 2):

1. Procedural monitoring of pilot implementation and respective outcomes towards anticipated project impacts with a focus on monitoring inclusive engagement targets.
2. Ex-post assessment of the joint impact of Urban ReLeaf city pilots on society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance, using the standardised MICS platform approach as well as dedicated and city-specific assessments of pilot impacts on governance and policy.
3. Exploratory cost-benefit analysis.
4. Communicating impact results to different audiences, using impact stories.

Figure 2: Overview of Urban ReLeaf impact and evaluation framework.

The following chapters describe the four building blocks of the framework in more detail.

3 Process and outcome monitoring towards impact

This first building block of the framework focuses on the procedural monitoring of city pilot implementation and respective outcomes towards anticipated project impacts with a focus on monitoring inclusive engagement targets. On the one hand, it is rooted in the process of required progress monitoring of the EC as the funding entity of the project, as well as in the need to address a pertinent challenge in citizen science and public participation: inclusive engagement.

3.1 Urban ReLeaf outcomes towards impact

As part of its intervention logic, Urban ReLeaf has formulated several desirable outcomes on the way to impact, associated results and associated targets to help measure if goals have been achieved. Table 1 outlines the outcomes, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to tangible results and targets which are most relevant for the assessment of city pilots and their contributions to overall project impact.

Table 1: Expected outcomes towards impacts relevant to Urban ReLeaf city pilots extracted from full project table, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for results and established targets.

Outcomes towards impact	Result KPIs	Targets
1. A more widespread participation of citizens in the monitoring, observation, and protection of the urban environment.	Number of citizens mobilised	250 to 1000 per city pilot
	Minimum share of women participants	50%
	Share of marginalised and vulnerable groups (as per adopted definition)	30-40%
	Underrepresented geographic city areas reached	One per city
2. Greater availability of qualitative and quantitative in-situ data for long time series and better geographical coverage, contributing to the in-situ component of existing observation systems.	Total number of in-situ qualitative/quantitative measurements across cities	500-10,000
	Temperature/humidity/air-quality time-series contribution to GEOSS.	1-3 years' time-series duration
3. Broader use of data and information collected by citizens in policy and research , with crowdsourcing and citizen observations acknowledged as valuable information complementary to authoritative observations.	Number of stakeholders participating in policy processing mapping and co-design strategies workshops	75-120 total; 12-20/city
	Number of data portals/ knowledge hubs that will integrate citizen observations	Min 1/city (if available)
	TRL advancements and TRL levels reached	Levels 6-8 across all technologies
	Number of policies that will make direct use of the data	Min 1/city
4. Increased use of existing toolkits and development of new toolboxes.	Number of new toolkits and toolboxes developed	1 toolkit; 1 tree registry (app/platform); 1 perceptions app

	Number of participants in the Design for Business sprints	20-30/city
	Number of participants in the Pop-up Community Labs	30-40/city
	Accelerator cities recruited for tools and technology uptake	Up to 10
5. Leveraged use of wearables for citizens and other low-cost technologies in the domain of environmental observation.	Number of low-cost sensors/ wearables deployed by the cities in the project	300-600 total across 6 cities
	Number of cities to sustain wearables/low-cost sensors for future solutions	6
	Number of citizens mobilised using the technologies to collect data	250 to 1000 per city pilot

This notion of outputs monitoring and describing progress towards achieving impacts will be accomplished as part of regular progress updates and the periodic project review process and reporting put in place by the EC, as the main funding body of Urban ReLeaf.

3.2 Monitoring and evaluation of inclusive engagement aspirations and targets

Evaluating the citizen science campaigns in city pilots is essential for understanding the overall outcomes and pinpointing operational strengths and weaknesses. This process promotes accountability by involving diverse stakeholders, including participants, the public, and potential funders, and emphasises inclusivity (Kieslinger et al., 2017). This section addresses the engagement and participation of citizens as citizen science participants within the activities of the six pilots, focusing particularly on inclusivity (see Appendix 1 – Social vulnerability in Urban ReLeaf). In the city pilots, socially vulnerable groups can be identified through the analysis of socio-economic and spatial information, or through participative investigation of local specific contexts (or a combination). People must not be stigmatised or labelled into a category without investigating the specific vulnerability and impacts in context. As such, it relates directly to Outcome 1 above “A more widespread participation of citizens in the monitoring, observation, and protection of the urban environment” (Table 1).

The KPIs to be met, developed according to the CREAM criteria, are the following:

- Number of citizens mobilised: 250 to 1000 per city pilot
- Minimum share of women participants: 50%
- Marginalized and vulnerable groups: 30-40%
- Underrepresented geographic city areas reached: One per city

Additionally, the monitoring and evaluation strategies of the inclusive engagement aspirations and targets in Urban ReLeaf city pilots do not only aim to verify whether the predefined KPIs are met. This monitoring will also be directed towards addressing frustrations, challenges, and difficulties experienced by participants. As such, monitoring participation rates and changes in motivations over time is also important. It should therefore be ensured that participants can voice their opinions about different aspects of the project throughout the different stages. Following the SPICED criteria,

feedback will be collected about both the processes and eventual outcomes, with the possibility to mitigate and implement solutions based on this insight.

The findings from the monitoring can be shared with participants and the wider citizen science community such as through scientific articles and best-practice stories about recruitment and retention of participants.

3.3 Data collection methods and instruments

Overall, most of the indicators can and have partly already been monitored through various instruments, including events logs, statistics on data platforms (e.g., for tracking number of collected in-situ data points), registration surveys or app registrations. To identify the number of policies that will make direct use of the collected data by citizens, a survey and dialogues with city pilot partners will be the main source of information. In this case, we can already anticipate that the realisation of this outcome may vary across cities. For the monitoring and evaluating of inclusive engagement, the following approaches are considered (see Appendix 2 for further details):

- A participant survey with questions about socio-economic (SE) and socio-demographic (SD) characteristics to monitor diversity can be completed at the start of the activities (when registering for the campaign), or at the end of a specific activity or study. It is best that these questions are asked at the end of an activity to avoid the effect of 'priming'. This is a bias (activating a stereotype) that can be created when asking respondents to provide demographic information before completing a survey or an activity, and which might cause a significant decrease in performance (Fernandez et al., 2016). Examples of SE and SD questions to include in a survey are provided in Appendix 2.
- Event and activity logs whereby the date, location, role in the activities, retention rates, number of hours, etc. are tracked. A part of these data could be collected through of the mobile applications such as retention rates, number of hours, etc., a template is provided for the manual and digital logging of activities (see Appendix 2 - Events or Activity logging). This template could be potentially merged with the communication and dissemination logging of WP6.
- Interviews or focus groups can be organised with participants for collecting more in-depth feedback about benefits and challenges of participation.
- Observations of meetings can also be conducted with post-briefing sessions. A survey template (Appendix 2 – Observation of meetings / community participation) is foreseen for the pilot coordinators to distribute at the end of an activity. The questionnaire is taken from (Goodman et al., 1996) and adjusted to the context of Urban ReLeaf. The measures evaluated in this form are organisation, participation, leadership, decision making, conflict resolution, cohesion, and productivity. This survey can be combined with the SD and SE characteristics.
- Finally, interviews with the different pilot coordinators can be organised to collect information about their experience in implementing inclusive citizen science activities, the challenges, benefits, and lessons learned.

Overall, monitoring and evaluating progress and set targets align with the CREAM and SPICED criteria (see Table 2) and allow the project team to take stock, check assumptions and adjust activities accordingly. Furthermore, the evaluation will provide solid cumulative evidence to be available at the end of the project for summative reporting and communications to further maximise impact.

Table 2: Characteristics matrix and rapid assessment for process and outcome monitoring focused on inclusive engagement targets.

Primary purpose	To monitor the inclusive participation of citizens in the six city pilots.	
Secondary purpose	To provide timely information for learning and corrective action to iterate engagement approaches to ensure respective inclusion targets are met.	
Target audiences	Urban ReLeaf project team, participating citizens and stakeholders, European Commission	
CREAM Criteria	Application	Limitations
<i>Clear</i>	KPIs are observable, verifiable numbers.	N/A
<i>Relevant</i>	KPIs appropriately translate the participation of people from vulnerable groups within the Urban ReLeaf activities.	N/A
<i>Economic</i>	KPIs can be measured during planned pilot activities, or represent minimal additional costs (e.g., through online survey or online interviews).	Does represent an additional effort for the pilot coordinators. Routine protocol for monitoring inclusive participation should be adopted by the pilot coordinators.
<i>Adequate</i>	KPIs adequately report on the participation of people from vulnerable groups within the Urban ReLeaf activities.	Drop-out or low participation of citizens in monitoring and evaluation activities can affect adequacy of results. Reasons linked to (lack of) participation might be missed with current indicators and will be mitigated through qualitative assessment.
<i>Monitorable</i>	KPIs can be relatively well and easily assessed, e.g., during planned pilot activities.	Data collection should not be intrusive or bring participants in a pressured situation. Different methods are used to monitor the indicators.
SPICED criteria	Application	Limitations
<i>Subjective</i>	Qualitative approaches enable the capture of unique and critical insights from first-hand sources (i.e., participants and pilot coordinators)	N/A
<i>Participatory</i>	Further indicators are decided amongst pilot coordinators and other relevant partner of the consortium.	N/A
<i>Interpreted</i>	KPIs are described in a clear and accessible way.	N/A
<i>Cross-checked</i>	The different evaluation methods listed above enable to cross-check and validate the indicators.	N/A

<i>Empowering</i>	The continuous monitoring enables a constant reflection regarding the inclusivity of the activities and enable the implementation of mitigation tracks.	N/A
<i>Diverse</i>	The diverse approaches will involve a range of stakeholders.	N/A

The next section will describe the approach for measuring the wider joint impact of Urban ReLeaf city pilots on society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance, using the MICS platform approach as well as more specific, city-tailored assessments of impacts on governance and policy.

4 Pilot impact assessment

4.1 Measuring joint impact of city pilots using the MICS platform

The MICS off-the-shelf approach was chosen to assess the joint wider impacts of Urban ReLeaf pilots as part of the ex-post assessment. The approach was considered suitable enough for the intended purpose and audiences as well as sufficiently fulfilling the CREAM criteria (Table 3).

Table 3: Characteristics matrix and rapid assessment for using the MICS approach in Urban ReLeaf. Deciding factors are highlighted in grey.

Primary purpose	To assess overarching and joint wider impacts of Urban ReLeaf pilots on society, economy, environment, science/technology, and governance.	
Secondary purpose	To contribute to citizen science specific impact assessment and provide information for comparisons across citizen science projects.	
Main target audiences	Citizen science community, European Commission, policy makers	
CREAM Criteria	Application	Limitations
<i>Clear</i>	MICS questions are clear and additional information and help is provided as well as links to original sources.	N/A
<i>Relevant</i>	Overall, the domains covered (society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance) are highly relevant to Urban ReLeaf.	The approach addresses a bird's eye view and works on a high-level rather than a more specific and targeted scale.
<i>Economic</i>	Relative to the breadth of domains covered, the efforts required to complete the assessment are manageable.	N/A
<i>Adequate</i>	Approach can provide sufficiently insightful information when pilots are jointly considered.	The MICS platform approach is based on a deterministic and standardised approach, which cannot completely account for or relate to contextual specificity, distinct goals or unique insights.
<i>Monitorable</i>	Yes, information can be collected building synergies with existing data sources in the project.	N/A

MICS: Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen-science impacts on the environment and society was a three-year Horizon 2020 project (2019-2022) to create a platform which can be used to assess the impact of citizen science projects at different stages of the project cycle from beginning to project completion and beyond. The MICS platform provides a clear framework and standardised approach for measuring impacts to make citizen science more efficient and effective, reduce costs, and spread the use of citizen science more widely (Ceccaroni et al., 2022). It can be used by any citizen science project and allows comparison across a wide range of projects. The MICS integrated platform of metrics and instruments help measure the broad impacts of citizen science projects in the following domains:

- Society: impact on society and individuals, collective values, understanding, actions and well-being.

- Economy: impact on the production and exchange of goods and services, entrepreneurial activity, and economic benefits derived from citizen science data.
- Environment: impact on the bio-chemical-physical environment.
- Science and technology: impact on the scientific system, process and knowledge, including scientific paradigms and resulting technological artefacts and standards.
- Governance: impact on formal and informal decision-making processes and institutions, on relationships/partnerships, and the governance of citizen science data.

The MICS framework is comprised of more than 200 questions and related impacts and indicators (Ceccaroni et al., 2022), which can also be accessed in full on the MICS website (<https://about.mics.tools/questions>). Example of one MICS question in the Society domain (impact highlighted in bold) can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: MICS Impact questions (left column) are complemented by a Help and Information as well as a Source column. Retrieved from <https://about.mics.tools/questions#society> (16/4/2024).

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
67 (167)	<p>Does the project lead to an increased level of trust among participants and other stakeholders?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> As part of the Ground Truth 2.0 project, Wehn et al. investigated several aspects of trust within both neighbourhoods and online communities. You can read a summary of the methods used on about.mics.tools as well as links to a full description of the questions used in interviews.</p>	<p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Does engagement in the project influence the level of trust, confidence, or respect among citizen participants and project leaders?</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Greater ownership through involvement at every stage, including motivations for monitoring and action, increased trust, tolerance and attitudes to nature.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Trust and belonging (neighbourhood) Trust and belonging are important indicators of how much people care about their mutual environment. It is linked to the likelihood with which they will participate in decision making if it concerns their neighbourhood. Trust and belonging are measured with the presence of mutual concerns and shared values amongst neighbours and an emotional connection to the neighbourhood or city.</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2014: Shared understanding; consensus on the topic; fishing agreement in place; less intervillage conflict; communication and collaboration is increased; trust has increased between partners</p>

The questions feed into high-level MICS indicator domains, which are:

- Activeness and Involvement (Society)
- Economic productivity and Financial sustainability (Economy)
- Environmental awareness and Environmental footprint (Environment)
- Scientific productivity and Interdisciplinary science (Science and technology)
- Policy and Sustainable Development Goals (Governance)

Once all information and answers to questions are entered in the MICS platform, the system generates rule-based and machine learning scores, an impact summary report as well as a list of recommendations to increase impact potential of the assessed project (see Annex 1 for an example of a MICS report for the *D-Noses* project). Urban ReLeaf is planning to gather all relevant information from the six pilots via multiple project information channels and sources to jointly complete the MICS assessment. For full transparency and to form a comprehensive and coherent assessment across the six Urban ReLeaf pilots, the assessment report (D2.4) will not only include the results created by MICS, i.e., the auto-generated scores and MICS impact summary but also the information and answers entered to feed the assessment, together with explanation notes where relevant.

4.2 Urban ReLeaf approach for capturing impacts on policy and governance

4.2.1 Developing a tailored approach

The development consists of several activities which culminate in the consolidation of a tailored approach for Urban ReLeaf.

Activity 1: Review of existing assessment approaches focusing on impacts on policy and governance.

Existing frameworks in citizen science and research more broadly which (partly) distinctly assess impacts on policy and governance were considered to inform a tailored Urban ReLeaf approach. The reviewed literature includes the governance indicator set on the MICS Impact Indicator Explorer⁴, the Impact Assessment Methodological Framework of the ACTION project (Passani et al., 2020), the CSISTA approach (Wehn et al., 2021a), the use of logic models in the DITOs project (Skarlatidou and Haklay, 2021), a quantitative survey developed to study transformative impact for science, citizen empowerment and socio-political processes in Germany, Austria and Switzerland (von Gönner et al., 2023), a literature review on scientific, social and political impact of social sciences and humanities research (Reale et al., 2018) and the Research Infrastructures' Impact Assessment Toolkit⁵ and related Guidebook (Griniece et al., 2020), amongst others.

The approaches were screened and those that seemed applicable to the policy context of Urban ReLeaf were mapped against each other to look for distinctions, overlaps and coherence overall. First insights reveal that impact categorisations and indicators vary greatly. There is considerable semantic ambiguity across terms and no overarching conceptualisation is applied to or can be derived from it. Furthermore, the aspect of data governance, which is a critical aspect in Urban ReLeaf's considerations about policy and governance impact is largely missing in these approaches and frameworks. Hence, Urban ReLeaf may take inspiration from them, as well as select

⁴ <https://about.mics.tools/domain-governance>, accessed 25/04/2024. The MICS Impact Indicator Explorer is a complementary service to the automated assessment on the MICS platform, where different domain specific indicators can be chosen for more tailored and contextualised assessment.

⁵ <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en>, accessed on 25/04/2024.

individual aspects to include in its own, but they cannot be reused in a simple way without major adaptation.

Activity 2: Review of policy and governance models

In addition, existing theories and models of public policy and (urban/data) governance are considered to ground the Urban ReLeaf approach in domain-specific literature more generally rather than just in impact assessment approaches for (citizen) science, which already form a level of abstracted application of such concepts. Policy and governance models and theories reviewed from the literature include, amongst others, The Governance Analytical Framework (GAF) to investigate policy processes (Hufty, 2011), the institutional dimension of urban politics and governance (Pierre, 1999), diverse forms of participation in contemporary, complex governance (Arnstein, 1969; Fung, 2006), heuristics of relations between citizen science and governance (Göbel et al., 2019), the concept of “shadow of hierarchy” as an incentive for governments and the public to engage in non-hierarchical policy making and service provision (Börzel and Risse, 2010), the idea of “Enabling Governance Arrangements” (University of Freiburg, 2021), and different models of the policy process, including critiques of using too simplistic concepts such as the policy cycle model (Bio Innovation Service, 2018; Cairney, 2015; Griniece et al., 2020). The exploration of some of the relevant literature suggests a wide debate about the different understandings and models of public policy and governance. The challenge is to strike the right balance and finding models which can serve pragmatic purposes (such as providing operational conceptualisations for an impact assessment) as well as address complexity and uncertainty.

Activity 3: Co-creation with project partners

To ensure that the developed approach, anticipated impacts and possible indicators are informed by, and well rooted in the respective contexts and policy realities of the cities, a co-creation activity took place during the Urban ReLeaf General Assembly in Utrecht at the beginning of April 2024 (Figure 3).

This workshop is part of a series of activities with relevant partners and stakeholders to surface assumptions held about potential impacts and public policy and governance and co-identify relevant impact and indicator spaces for consideration in the assessment.

Figure 3: Images illustrating collaborative activity to discuss impact and indicators at the Urban ReLeaf General Assembly 2024.

Partners, coming from business, design, academia, public service/policy and public administrations were grouped randomly around five tables to discuss the following question, using the thoughts bingo technique: What – based on your experience and given your professional perspective – can qualify as impacts on public policy and governance and the acceptance and uptake of citizen observations in authoritative processes, considering different aspects such as workflows, structures, people (roles, culture, skill), or data? Participants had time for individual considerations which were then shared and discussed in more depth in the group. This first exercise was followed by a discussion of possible (suitable/feasible) indicators for observing the identified impacts, considering the question of how and through which actions, signs, manifestation would the relevant changes and impacts be identified. The following example was given to help differentiate the notion of impact and indicator:

IMPACT
Increased institutional commitment to citizen science.

INDICATORS
Public statement issued on institute website.
Increased share of budget for citizen science activities.
Dedicated job post to support citizen science activities.

The individual inputs and group discussions were documented using physical post-its and the miro platform (Figure 4) and are analysed to feed into the ongoing development of the tailored approach.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the miro workspace for the collaborative activity to discuss impact and indicators at the Urban ReLeaf General Assembly 2024.

Activity 4: Collecting baseline information

Baseline information describes key conditions within a given context at the start of a project to inform, amongst others, the later assessment of changes and impacts (Bamberger, 2010; IFRC Planning & Evaluation Department, 2013; Tirnauer, 2010). Without any baseline data, it is difficult to derive insights about the project's contribution to changes and its impacts on, in this case of Urban ReLeaf, the urban policy and governance domain. In addition, baseline information can be used to inform project management, fine tune future assessments, ensure accountability, promote stakeholder participation, shape expectations and feed into communication strategies as well as justify project interventions (IFRC Planning & Evaluation Department, 2013). Baseline information can be collected before or at the start of a project or intervention, or reconstructed using secondary data, project administrative data, or deploying recall techniques (Bamberger, 2010).

Urban ReLeaf considers three main sources for baseline information about policy and governance aspects to inform the tailored ex-post assessment and to help identify changes and impacts that can – at least in part – be attributed to the project's activities.

1. One of the first activities in Urban ReLeaf (within the first six months of the project) was to capture the wider **urban policy landscape** in the six Urban ReLeaf cities, focusing on the topics of urban greening, climate change adaptation, citizen science and inclusive citizen participation. 28 urban policy and strategy documents were analysed. Additionally, city partners conducted 35 interviews with stakeholders within the city administrations and the urban public policy context. The topics that were covered in the interviews included the specific situation of urban greening, climate and public participation, the future vision of the city, the envisioned role of citizens within greenspace policy and management, the relevant stakeholder ecosystem, and existing initiatives, as well as existing data tools and platforms (e.g., Digital Twin initiatives) to support urban planning and policy making. The results of the policy analysis

and interviews were published in the deliverable report *D2.1 Landscape report on policy processes and opportunities for inclusive participation* (Temmerman et al., 2023) and serve as important baseline information on the cities' climate change and urban greening agendas as well as the perceived role and state of citizens in urban policy, planning and governance.

2. In parallel to the above, a thorough **mapping of the respective urban data ecosystems** of the six cities was conducted using the ODI Data Landscape Playbook⁶. The exercise identified relevant datasets in use by or available to city administrations, as well as practices related to data asset quality, ethical considerations, and accessibility and openness of data. The analysis was published in the deliverable report *D3.1 Urban ReLeaf data ecosystem map* (Karagiannopoulou, 2023) and provides critical baseline information about different aspects related to data governance.
3. Additionally, a **baseline survey** was completed by each city pilot individually at the end of March 2024, before the citizen science campaigns and interventions with and for citizens started. This survey is based on the MICS governance indicators and questions, which were slightly adapted to fit the situational context of the project (see Appendix 3). Taken by each city individually, the results provide baseline insights which can be compared across cities and considered individually for the final assessment.

Activity 5: Validating and consolidating insights into a coherent, tailored approach

Once activities 1-4 are finalised, the respective results will be brought together to create a draft approach, which will be discussed and validated with relevant project partners to inform further adaptations and refinements.

One expectation is that this tailored approach will remain flexible and adaptive to account for systemic complexities and uncertainties and to remain receptive to the unfolding of impacts that were unexpected or have not been anticipated as such.

Also, Urban ReLeaf will likely work with the notion of dynamic impact and indicator spaces rather than too fixed and statically pre-determined indicators to be able to capture different impact dimensions based on governance, policy and public participation theory and models.

4.2.2 Data collection methods and instruments

The most suitable data collection methods and tools will be chosen to best support the tailored approach. They will be reported on in D4.10. The assumption is that synergies can be found with the methods already mentioned in previous chapters, including surveys, interviews, focus groups, event observations, screening of diverse materials, including publications and communications, amongst others.

The development of the tailored approach is overall also guided by CREAM and SPICED criteria. In this case, they are used prescriptively to ensure suitability of the approach in terms of its effectiveness and efficiency.

⁶ <https://open-data-institute.gitbook.io/data-landscape-playbook>, accessed 26/04/2024.

5 Exploratory cost-benefit analysis

An additional exploratory and mixed methods cost-benefit analysis is envisioned to complement prior approaches and to enable diverse perspectives on the possible effects and benefits of Urban ReLeaf pilots and the chosen citizen science method. Like the tailored assessment, the approach for the exploratory cost-benefit analysis is in development using CREAM criteria prescriptively to ensure overall effectiveness and efficiency.

Generally, cost benefit analyses can be both quantitative and qualitative and they include three main steps: identifying and describing costs and benefits, attributing costs and benefits and comparing costs and benefits. A quantitative analysis will express costs/benefits largely in monetary and numeric terms whereas a qualitative analysis draws on a range of information sources and produces qualitative insights (Stevens et al., 2008).

5.1 Cost-benefit in citizen science

Deliberate considerations about costs and benefits in citizen science started about a decade ago (Blaney et al., 2016; Goldstein et al., 2014) and since then, only a small number of studies have investigated costs and benefits with apparent variations in conceptualisations, use of terminology and associated methodologies (Alfonso et al., 2022). They range from assessing total expenditures for running a citizen science campaign vs. professional staff cost for conducting similar research activities (Encarnação et al., 2021), the valorisation of citizen science interventions for reducing social vulnerability (Ferri et al., 2020) and estimations for cost per observation (Davids et al., 2019), to combining cost per observation with assessments of data complementarity (Alfonso et al., 2022). Recently, the YouCount project published a fully qualitative analysis of costs and benefits of citizen science using a multi-criteria framework covering dimensions very similar to the overarching impact domains mentioned in previous chapters (Franco et al., 2024).

5.2 Mixed qualitative–quantitative approach

In Urban ReLeaf, costs associated with citizen observations will be estimated in economic terms to investigate the claim for citizen science to lower cost compared to professional monitoring (Blaney et al., 2016), e.g., cost per citizen observation and equivalent labour costs saved, providing further insight in the viability of citizen engagement in urban monitoring. Additionally, surveys, interviews or focus groups will be conducted with city partners to understand people’s perceptions of non-monetary costs and benefits. These will likely shape assumptions and decision about whether city administrations will invest in citizen science-based approaches and citizen observatories in the future.

Urban ReLeaf campaigns suitable for analysis of cost and benefit perceptions

In principle, all Urban ReLeaf pilots and campaigns are suitable for a qualitative assessment of the perceptions of costs and benefits held by city partners at later stages of the project.

Urban ReLeaf campaigns suitable for monetary cost-based analysis

One underlying assumption to identify suitable campaigns for the quantification of cost is that the data collected could also be collected by staff from city administrations or research organisations. For example, the air quality and tree registry campaigns in Riga and Athens, can, in principle, be reduced to monetary terms to understand directly associated economic costs. Cost associated with generating PM_{2.5} observations include, e.g., personnel time, electricity cost, Wi-Fi- and internet cost and materials to mount the sensors. In contrast, the greenspace perceptions campaigns and heat stress campaigns in Cascais, Dundee and Utrecht focus on specific individual perceptions and observations from the public as important datapoints which cannot be substituted by administration staff.

6 Communicating impact with impact stories

Assessing and documenting impact is essential to legitimise project actions, but it is the way in which outcomes and impacts are communicated and perceived by relevant audiences which will maximise the potential for impacts to materialise and unfold further effects in the public realm. Urban ReLeaf will ensure to use several pathways and channels to communicate its impacts using the concept of impact stories and storytelling.

Communication pathway 1: Storytelling for two

One of the main pathways to communicate the evidenced outcomes and impacts of Urban ReLeaf pilots will align and follow the overarching Urban ReLeaf communications strategy of “Storytelling for two”. It emphasises the need to create compelling narratives that will encourage people to share them with others. Storytelling involves designing communication rhythms, messages, and visual media that reinforce key messages and encourage participation. This concept will be applied to tailor impact messages and language to capture the respective audience's attention (Woods and Veeckman, 2023).

Communication pathway 2: Impact stories and impact briefs

Drawing on the CSISTA approach (Wehn et al., 2021a), specific impact briefs and impact stories will be developed for the respective cities to support and strengthen interactions with policy makers on different levels, within city administrations, on a national and international level.

Communication pathway 3: Urban ReLeaf toolbox and roadmap

Urban ReLeaf will also produce the Urban ReLeaf toolkit for cities to develop data-driven and citizen-powered urban greenspace monitoring approaches, drawing from and enriched by generated impact stories as case-specific insights. The toolkit will be accompanied by an adoption roadmap which provides actionable pathways for public authorities, civil society organisations, citizen science practitioners for the use of citizen data in environmental action and reporting.

Communication pathway 4: Accelerator programme

Additionally, Urban ReLeaf will develop and implement an accelerator programme to promote citizen- and data-driven urban innovation internationally, supported by the impact stories from the six Urban ReLeaf cities. The programme will select up to 10 accelerator cities to participate in a webinar series and F-2-F workshops. The focus will be to support local government staff and representatives from civil society in the uptake of citizen observations in their local planning, reporting and decision-making. Urban ReLeaf city partners will participate in the online webinar series and F-2-F events to showcase the city pilot's outcomes and impacts.

7 Conclusions

This report outlines and describes the process and main building blocks of devising the Urban ReLeaf pilot evaluation and impact assessment framework. The framework is designed to address different purposes, audiences and topics. While such a multi-purpose and multi-level approach poses the risk of being too demanding, the framework tries to form effective synergies with related project activities (project reporting, communications, capitalising on prior activities for baselining etc.), make use of off-the-shelf methods, such as the MICS platform and only tailors methodologies where relevant and necessary. In the subsequent months, and years, the framework and related methods will be refined and implemented. The results will be published in the deliverable report *D4.10 Urban ReLeaf pilots evaluation report and impact briefs* before project end and communicated and disseminated via multiple channels and activities as outlined in chapter 6.

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Appendix 1 – Social vulnerability in Urban ReLeaf

In the context of the Urban ReLeaf project, citizens are invited to participate in data-driven decision-making processes for inclusive and green urban transitions. With this mission, the project supports *SDG 10 Reduce inequality: support the marginalized and disadvantaged* and provides new data streams for monitoring *SDG 11.7 Universal access to safe, inclusive, and accessible, green and public spaces*. The collected data can support cross-sectoral innovation and political agenda setting for climate change adaptation and green infrastructure in urban environments.

The Urban ReLeaf pilot cities will address topics of air quality, heat stress and green infrastructure (tree management), and use citizen observations for urban planning. These initiatives are in line with their climate action plans in pursuit of building climate resilience (e.g., climate neutrality by 2030), and keeping cities liveable and accessible for all.

When recruiting and engaging citizens, the Urban ReLeaf city pilots consider that climate change does not affect all citizens in the same way. In many European countries, there is a disproportionate exposure and uneven distribution of impacts of air pollution and extreme temperatures which reflect the socio-demographic differences within society. The reason why individuals may be more vulnerable to the impacts of environmental risks are related to the specific circumstances of the individual, such as their age, health condition, and particular behaviours. This specific type of vulnerability is labelled as '**social vulnerability**' (Breil et al., 2018) It is an integrated measure of exposure and susceptibility to harm, and the lack of capacity to avoid, cope with or adapt to environmental health hazards. The sensitivity is largely driven by age and health, while the ability to cope is linked to the socio-economic status, social support available or awareness of risks.

Based on studies of the European Environment Agency (Breil et al., 2018; European Environment Agency, 2018), the following socially vulnerable groups are likely to be affected by exacerbating environmental threats and sit within the general scope of Urban ReLeaf vulnerable audiences⁷:

- **Women** are generally considered more vulnerable than men, because they have, on average, more limited access to resources, less access to justice, limited mobility, and a limited voice in shaping decisions, and influencing policy especially in low-income countries. The following factors make women generally more vulnerable than men, including gender related socio-economic (e.g., education, level of unpaid work), legal (e.g., inheritance rights), political (e.g., participation in governance) disadvantages, socio-cultural (e.g., use of public services), and physical and biological differences (e.g., life expectancy, ability to cope with high temperatures).
- **Elderly people** are a group consistently listed as vulnerable or heavily affected by climate-related events such heat waves due to physiological factors.

⁷ This list is not comprehensive and other categories may fall within the definition of being socially vulnerable to (extreme) environmental conditions which affect well-being. The list outlines a range of potential vulnerable audiences suitable for the Urban ReLeaf project.

- **Infants and young children:** young children are more prone to heat-related illnesses because of their less developed thermoregulation and limited ability to influence their surroundings. Children also have higher respiratory rates than adults and may inhale higher levels of pollutants than adults. Furthermore, children's immune systems and developing organs are not yet mature and therefore more affected. Children also participate to a lesser extent in decision-making processes around urbanization and land use planning.
- **People in poor health** are more prone to heat-related mortality and health impacts, especially those with renal or cardiovascular health issues and those who are bed-bound.
- **Groups or individuals with a lower socio-economic status** (people who are unemployed, have a level of income or education below average): This group tends to live, work, and go to school in places with worse air quality and are exposed to higher temperatures. Poorer communities are also more likely to live in housing of poor quality, which may be prone to overheating. Due to their financial constraints, they also have more difficulties to prepare for extreme weather events and to recover afterwards.
- **People with low literacy skills:** People who are not able to understand information about climate-related hazards may have a reduced individual ability to prepare and respond. They may also have no access to internet or digital technologies. Therefore, illiterate groups or those with limited knowledge of the official language, including refugees and immigrants, are also more vulnerable.
- **People with poor social networks:** Isolated people are less likely to receive information and help. The lack of social networks is particularly frequent among older people, people in poor health or with disabilities, people living alone, ethnic minorities, etc.
- **People living in areas most susceptible to harm from air pollution or high temperatures:** neighbourhoods with lots of grey infrastructure and a lack of relief areas, chronically deprived areas.

In the city pilots, socially vulnerable groups can be identified through the analysis of socio-economic and spatial information, or through participative investigation of local specific contexts (or a combination of the two). People must not be stigmatised or labelled into a category without investigating the specific vulnerability and impacts in context.

Appendix 2 – Data collection tools to monitor inclusive engagement

SE and SD Survey questions⁸

1) What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Another option (specify)
- I prefer not to answer.

2) How old are you?

- Under 18
- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65 – 74 years old
- Above 75 years old
- I prefer not to answer.

3) (For youth) What is the highest level of education that your *father* completed?

- No diploma
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Technical, trade or vocational school certificate or apprenticeship
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other degree:

4) (For youth) What is the highest level of education that your *mother* completed?

- No diploma
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Technical, trade or vocational school certificate or apprenticeship
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other degree:

5) What is your highest level of education that you completed?

- No diploma
- Primary education
- Secondary education

⁸ Based on (Berthold et al., 2023; Fernandez et al., 2016)

- Technical, trade or vocational school certificate or apprenticeship
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other degree:

6) To what extent do you agree with the following statements:

(Strongly disagree – disagree – neither disagree, nor agree – agree – strongly agree)

- I am content with my financial situation.
- I must save up to make ends meet.
- I get by well with my income.

Events or Activity logging

Manual logging of events

Pilot city	Activity type	Start date	End date	Presence (list)	City
Country	Total number of attendees	Total number of no-shows	Level of participation	Types of actions	Financial incentive

Type of activity (list)

- Workshop (ideation, data collection, analysis, etc.)
- Training (learning)
- Social event (community building)
- Focus group (research)
- Other type of activity

Total number of attendees (number of people who registered and showed up)

Total number of no-shows (number of people who registered but did not attend)

Level of participation (list)⁹

- Non-participation
- Low - Participants are manipulated (e.g., participants are decoration)
- Low - Participants are informed (e.g., participants are provided with information to assist them in understanding a problem)
- Middle - Participants are consulted (e.g., participants can give feedback on the analysis, or decisions – but their input is not binding)
- High - Participants are involved (e.g., participants are collaborators in each step of the process, and are included in the development of alternatives, Urban ReLeaf makes the final decision and initiates)
- High - Participants are collaborators and take full control (e.g., final decision-making is in hand of the participants, Urban ReLeaf implements what the participants decide, participants initiate)

⁹ Based on the ladder of citizen participation (Arnstein, 1969).

Types of actions (multiple options are possible, list)

- Formulating research questions (e.g., submitting ideas, expressing concerns, crowdsourcing challenges, etc.)
- Developing or choosing a method (e.g., becoming an interviewer, developing a measurement device, defining a survey protocol)
- Collecting data (e.g., submitting perceptions, collecting tree data, counting, observing, using sensors, etc.)
- Analysing data (e.g., annotating, transcribing, interpreting, summarizing, calculating, etc.)
- Reporting and dissemination (e.g., proposing new directions, formulating policy recommendations, co-authoring a publication, speaking at an event, etc.)
- Other type of action
- Not applicable

Incentive (a financial incentive was rewarded to the participants, e.g., a gift voucher)

- Yes
- No

Digital statistics¹⁰

- **Number of active days:** number of days a participant was using the mobile application and performed at least one task. (*Example: 3 days*)
- **Total days linked to the campaign:** the total number of days a participant is linked with a campaign from start till dropout day. (*Example: 10 days*)
- **Days until campaign finishes:** the total remaining days from dropout until end of the campaign. (*Example: 50 days*)
- **Activity ratio:** number of active days / total number of days linked to the campaign, i.e., the closer to 1 the more active a participant is during the days in a campaign. (*Example: 3 / 10 = 0.3*)
- **Relative activity ratio:** total number of days linked to the campaign / days until campaign finishes, the closer to 1, the longer a participant remains linked (persistent) to the project, from their joining to the end of the project. (*Example: 10 / 50 = 0,2*)
- **Daily devoted time:** the averaged hours a participant executes tasks on each day the participant is active. (*Example: 2 hours*)
- **Lurking days:** the number of days a participant is using the application but without any active contribution. (*Example: 2 days*)
- **Lurking ratio:** is the proportion of days on which the participant was lurking in relation to the total days the participant visited the project (active + lurking days). The closer to 1 means the more a volunteer lurks (i.e., logs into the platform and browses content but does not contribute) during the days they are online. (*Example: 2 / 5 = 0,4*)

¹⁰ Based on the engagement metrics of (Aristeidou and Herodotou, 2020)

Observation of meetings community participation¹¹

1. How clear were the goals of this activity to you?

Poor (e.g., unclear, diffuse, conflicting, unacceptable)	Fair	Satisfactory (e.g., moderately clear, shared by some)	Good	Excellent (e.g., clear, shared by all, endorsed with enthusiasm)
1	2	3	4	5

2. What was your general level of participation in this activity?

Poor (e.g., was bored or distracted, low verbal participation)	Fair	Satisfactory (e.g., paid attention half of the time)	Good	Excellent (e.g., paid attention, participated in the discussion)
1	2	3	4	5

3. What was the leadership like in this activity?

Poor (e.g., there was no leadership)	Fair	Satisfactory (e.g., some direction was provided)	Good	Excellent (e.g., clear sense of direction was provided)
1	2	3	4	5

4. What was the quality of the decision-making at this activity?

Poor (e.g., decision were dominated by a few participants)	Fair	Satisfactory (e.g., about half of the participants took part)	Good	Excellent (e.g., everyone took part)
1	2	3	4	5

5. What was the cohesiveness among the participants in this activity?

Poor (e.g., little cohesion)	Fair	Satisfactory (e.g., moderate amount of cohesion)	Good	Excellent (e.g., participants worked well with each other)
1	2	3	4	5

6. Overall, how satisfied are you with this activity?

Very dissatisfied (e.g., not much accomplished, wasted my time)	Dissatisfied	Moderately satisfied (e.g., accomplished a moderate amount)	Satisfied	Very satisfied (e.g., much accomplished, good use of my time)
1	2	3	4	5

¹¹ Based on the 'meeting effectiveness inventory' survey (Goodman et al., 1996)

Appendix 3 – Urban ReLeaf governance baseline survey

Adapted from MICS governance indicators and questions:

<https://about.mics.tools/questions#governance>

Questions

How is the pilot managed?

- The pilot is run by a single organisation.
- The pilot is run by a group of organisations but led by a single organisation.
- The pilot is run by a group of organisations who lead equally.
- The pilot is run by citizens.
- Some other management structure.
- I don't know.

What type of organisation leads the pilot?

- Public body (including governments and municipalities)
- Sub- or adjacent organisations of public bodies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations
- Research-performing organisations (including universities)
- Business and industry (including private corporations, institutions, firms, and associations)
- Some other kind of other organisation
- I don't know.

What types of organisations are partners in running the pilot?

- Public bodies (including governments and municipalities)
- Sub- or adjacent organisations of public bodies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations
- Research-performing organisations (including universities)
- Business and industry (including private corporations, institutions, firms, and associations)
- Some other kind of organisation
- I don't know.

What types of organisations are involved with the pilot (but don't help to manage the pilot)?

- Public bodies (including governments and municipalities)
- Sub- or adjacent organisations of public bodies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations
- Research-performing organisations (including universities)
- Business and industry (including private corporations, institutions, firms, and associations)
- Some other kind of organisation
- No other organisations are involved with the pilot.
- I don't know.

Does the pilot explicitly foster new relationships among different stakeholders (not including those between citizens and scientists; so, for example, between public bodies and commercial organisations)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot collaborate with other initiatives to enhance mutual learning?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Which resources does the pilot directly share with other projects or initiatives at this point?

- Data
- Learnings
- Participants
- Instruments (for example, observation tools, protocols or sensors)
- Methodologies
- Resources on the theory and practice of citizen science
- Communication channels
- Other resources
- The pilot does not share resources with other initiatives yet.
- I don't know.

Among which of the following dimensions is the pilot planning to create institutional change (within the organisations associated with the pilot)?

- Open access/data: for example, development of a pilot specific/ organisational Data Management Plan
- Ethics: for example, creation of an ethics board, or employment of a quality assurance officer
- Gender equality: for example, development of a pilot specific/organisational Gender Equality Plan
- Public engagement
- Science education
- Responsible research and innovation: for example, development of organisational practices that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness or sustainability of research and innovation processes and products.
- The pilot is not planning to create institutional change among these dimensions.
- I don't know.
- Other

Are the outputs generated by the pilot planned to be open access?

- Yes, all outputs.
- Yes, some outputs.
- No
- I don't know.

How will the outputs generated by the pilot be usable by external parties?

- Outputs can be used without attribution to the authors.
- Outputs can be shared further.

- Outputs can be edited or combined with other material to produce a new work.
- Outputs can be used for commercial purposes.
- I don't know.

Does the pilot have a specific data management plan?

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but we are planning to create one.
- I don't know.

The following four questions focus on the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'. They focus on the data generated by the pilot, rather than on other outputs.

Will the data generated by the pilot be findable?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Will the data generated by the pilot be accessible?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Will the data generated by the pilot be interoperable?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Will the data generated by the pilot be reusable?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Apart from FAIR Guiding Principles, there are other ways to consider the pilot's data. For example...

Are data access rights clear and transparent?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Will or do other stakeholders already have more access to pilot data than participants (for example, access to raw data)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Are participants informed about where the data collected by the pilot are stored?

- Yes

- No
- I don't know.

Are participants informed about how the data collected and analysed by the pilot are used?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Are participants informed about whether the data collected by the pilot are shared?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot explicitly state which procedures it follows to ensure all data are collected and processed lawfully?

- Yes
- No
- The pilot doesn't need to ensure the data are collected lawfully.
- I don't know.

Does the pilot involve the collection of personal data of the participants?

- Yes, at least sometimes.
- No
- I don't know.

Do participants have to explicitly give consent (for example, signing a consent form) to take part in the pilot?

- Yes, at least sometimes.
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot have a specific code of ethics?

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but we are planning to have one.
- I don't know.

Will the code of ethics be made available to participants?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot include opportunities for pilot leaders and participants to discuss the ethical and political dimensions of the science involved?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot have explicit health and safety procedures in place?

- Yes

- No
- Not applicable
- I don't know.

Does the pilot have a specific risk management plan?

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but we are planning to create one.
- I don't know.

Have the organisations involved in the pilot increased their commitment to, or investment in, citizen science as a result of being involved in the project?

- Yes, they have made a formal commitment.
- Yes, but not as a formal commitment.
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot lead to an increase in the commitment of your organisation to public participation in decision making?

- Yes, we have made a formal commitment.
- Yes, but not as a formal commitment.
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot help your organisation to increase your capacity for facilitating public participation in decision making?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Are participants more actively involved in political processes as a result of taking part in the pilot?

- Yes, and it has been measured.
- Yes, but it has not been measured.
- Not yet
- No
- I don't know.

Have the pilot's results or findings supported authorities in enforcing existing regulations, laws, or policies?

- Yes
- Not yet
- No
- I don't know.

Have the pilot's results or findings been used as evidence in court (for example, for demonstrating environmental harm)?

- Yes
- Not yet
- No
- I don't know.

Which policy frameworks does the pilot consider?

- Organisational frameworks
- Local frameworks
- Regional frameworks
- National frameworks
- Global frameworks
- The pilot does not consider any policy frameworks.
- I don't know.
- Other

Does the pilot explicitly inform any governmental policy process?

- Yes, at the local level.
- Yes, at the regional level.
- Yes, at the national level.
- Yes, at the international level.
- Not yet
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot have any explicit impact on organisations external to the project and their structures and policies?

- Yes
- Not yet
- No
- I don't know.

Is the pilot team aware of what the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Is the pilot at all related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Which of the following Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is the pilot related to?

1. No Poverty
2. Zero Hunger
3. Good Health and Well-being
4. Quality Education
5. Gender Equality
6. Clean Water and Sanitation
7. Affordable and Clean Energy
8. Decent Work and Economic Growth
9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
10. Reducing Inequality
11. Sustainable Cities and Communities
12. Responsible Consumption and Production

- 13. Climate Action
- 14. Life Below Water
- 15. Life On Land
- 16. Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions
- 17. Partnerships for the Goals

Does the pilot involve data which match a specific indicator of a Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Does the pilot contribute data to the official reporting for a Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicator?

- Yes
- Not yet
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 1 – MICS impact summary report for the D-Noses project.

(Following pages)